

Environmental Behaviour of Pupil's and Teachers' Relationship

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ABSTRACT

Environmental education is being recognized as a very timely intervention for teacher education. The contributors have highlighted the findings of a research carried out in Bihar in respect of the environmental behaviour of pupil teachers and, based on this, they have recommended exclusive training for preservice as well as in-service teachers in this area. The major challenge before the human community is the need of developing environment interests and attitudes to protect it from further erosion, thus maintaining environmental values in the spirit that the Earth is our Mother, Obeyed as a Father and Nurtured as a Beloved Child. Etymologically environment means surroundings. It is the sum total of external factors, substances and conditions which influence organisms without their intrinsic part. Eco-restoration is closely related to eco-deterioration and utilization as well as replenishment of environment resources or eco-management. This requires a positive conduct of human behaviour or protective attitude towards environment. Pressure of population boom, uncontrolled and lavish consumption of natural resources, vast urbanization, industrial development and advances in science and technology and their application, coupled with huge energy utilization, have caused drastic ecological changes leading to serious environmental disorders. In the fact changing modern socio-economic scenario, there is a crisis of environmental awareness and acute dearth of responsible behaviour towards environment. This is no more a local problem. It has become a global disaster in the form of unmanageably increasing ecological imbalance.

Keywords: *Ecological imbalance, Communication, Responsibilities, Social Changing, Environment Values, Motivation*

The goal of environmental education is to improve all ecological relationships. Including that of mankind with nature and people in their surroundings. It may include conservation of energy and soil, protection of air, water and atmosphere against pollution, adequate utilization of locally available resources, creation of conducive atmosphere for living through socio-economic consciousness and preservation of natural resources to negate ecological imbalance. It is universally acknowledged that education is an effective medium of social reconstruction and, to a great extent, it offers solutions of the problems

our society is currently facing. Environmental education is the process of recognizing values and clarifying concepts in order to develop skills and attitudes necessary to understand and appreciate the interrelatedness among man, his culture and his biophysical surroundings. It provides every person with opportunities to acquire the knowledge, values, attitudes, commitment and skills needed to protect and improve the environment. Environmental education is essential for generating widespread awareness about environmental problems.

Teacher education is an integral component of the educational system. Teachers are the best

source of communication and implementation of desirable behaviours, attitudes and nurturing of values as well. Since they play a major role in education of children their own education is, therefore, a matter of vital concern. A teacher, being intimately connected with society and conditioned by the those, culture and character of the nation, acts as a messenger to convey the ideas in a perfect and prompt manner. Teacher education must, therefore, be intended to create necessary awareness among them about their roles and responsibilities, especially their behaviour towards environment.

For effective programming of environmental education, our teachers themselves should possess enough environmental awareness, positive environmental values and competency to achieve environmental objectives in relation with their students. They should know the prevailing environmental problems and the ways to overcome them as well as they must develop positive environmental values simultaneously without they won't be effective in performing their professional responsibilities. They have to carve the pupil to match with the needs of a dynamic and ever-changing social and natural environment. To face the present environmental situation, it is essential that everyone contributes in eliminating the causes responsible for ecological imbalance by restoring, developing and upholding environmental values.

Environmental Education in Bihar:

Bihar is a newly created state comprising largely of hilly districts. Ever since its origin, infrastructure activities have suddenly and rapidly been accelerated resulting into replacement of green forests by concrete jungles. Because of the so-called progressive activities, massive influx of gigantic machines, vehicles, builders and so many other infrasturctural equipments, stuffed with operational manpower, have invaded the

peace, tranquility, neatness, purity and scenic beauty of this picturesque hilly state which is yet more susceptible to any kind of environmental crisis. The state's mountains are geographically young and ecologically much fragile. Rapid growth of human population and over-exploitation of natural resources have led to the extinction of endangered local species, degradation and fragmentation of natural habitats. Habitat loss and people versus wildlife conflicts. As destruction of forests opens a Pandora's box for various environmental implications, it is almost necessary that people should be made environment conscious. This can be don through developing adequate awareness towards environment. Which can be inculcated in the school children or collegiate students and their teachers who can have this skill through their training programmes.

Envrionmental education in Bihar is necessary for awareness in the areas of soil erosion and its, to protect flora and fauna, to check uncontrolled influx of pilgrims and tourists and its effects, pollution increasing population, public health problems and proper utilization of natural resources. To meet the present dangerous environmental situation successfully, it is essential that everyone makes a contribution, which will emerge from proper training environmental education of pupil teachers, that is, "Work of each for the welfare of all".

The objectives of this study were:

To assess the environmental behaviour of pupil teachers of Bihar;

1. To study the influence of various factors viz age, marital status, medium of schooling, scheduled and non-scheduled caste category, gender and residing areas on the environmental behaviour of pupil teachers.
2. To recommend measures to combat the magnifying threat to environment.

From the review of related literature, it has been found that environmental studies in education in India do not match with the quantum of research carried out in other countries. At international level there have been repeated efforts to identify the problems and to stress the need and urgency of implementing the environmental education and research programmes on a very extensive scale.

Data Collection:

The present study was carried out on 352 pupil teachers (PTs) of B.Ed. Training colleges of Bihar. They were divided into two groups on the basis of their age. Age group 1 comprised of PTs up to the age of 25 years while age group 2 of above 25 years.

For the collection of data, the tool used was developed by the researchers themselves. The statements were selected with the help of experts in the field. The tool was evaluated for its reliability and validity to assess the environmental values of teachers and was found to be actually reliable and valid as well. It consisted of statements related to health, various kinds of pollution, different environmental problems, fertilizers and insecticides, plants and animals, frequent changing terrestrial climatic conditions on account of involvement of major part of the world in war amounting to extensive and excessive use of explosives or arsenic material, environmental policies and environmental values perceived and pursued.

Findings:

The result reveals that, out of 250 teachers studied, none of them was placed in group I; 44 were classified in group II; most of them, i.e., 175 were graded in group III, 13 were categorized in group IV while only 2 of them were classified in group V. In other words, out of 352 teachers most of them, i.e., 83% had average environmental values, 12.5% had little or poor values in this respect whereas only

3.7% had good environment values.

Total 250 pupil teachers were studied, 321 were of age group 1, i.e., up to the age of 25 years while 121 were of above 25 years of age. The mean value and S.D. of pupil teachers' environmental values belonging to age group 1 was found to be 47.4 and 7.22 respectively whereas the same for the pupil teachers of age group 2 was observed to be 47 and 7.89 in the same order. From the analysis, it can be interpreted that since there was no significant difference between the environmental values of pupil teachers of the age group 1 and 2, there was no effect of age on the environmental values of pupil teachers.

Total 352 PTs were studied, out of whom 211 were from urban areas while 141 were from rural background. The mean values of environmental awareness of urban and rural PTs were found to be 47.3 and 45.9 whereas S.D. was 6.6 and 8.9 in the same order. No significant difference, thus, appeared between the environmental values of urban and rural PTs. Though the PTs of urban area have a little edge over those of rural areas, there is no remarkable effect of the residing area on the environmental values of PTs. However, comparatively, PTs from urban areas have slightly more environmental values than those who come from rural areas.

While 352 PTs were evaluated, 245 were of general category and 107 belonged to the scheduled category. The mean and S.D. value for PTs belonging to general category was calculated as 46.8 and 7.7 respectively whereas for those pertaining to the scheduled category, it was counted to be 46.7 and 7.4 in the same order. Therefore, no significant difference between the environmental values of general and scheduled caste categories of PTs was noticed. The environmental values of the PTs belonging to general and scheduled caste categories are almost the same.

While studying the influence of medium of education on environmental values of PTs, total of 352 numbers were classified as 289 belonging to Hindi medium and 63 to English medium. The mean and S.D. value for the PTs having English medium background was calculated as 44.8 and 10.2 respectively whereas the same for the PTs coming from Hindi medium was found to be 46.7 and 7.9 in the same order. It was found that there is no significant difference between the environmental values of PTs belonging to the said two mediums of their education. It may, therefore, be concluded that medium of education of PTs does not play any role in their environmental values. However, apparently PTs from Hindi medium schooling have an edge over those who come from English medium.

To achieve this goal, a social movement is desperately required to amend the damaging behaviour of people towards environment. To launch a crusade against rapid destruction of environment, a campaign for educating people to protect the environment can only be carried out by the teachers who are the real craftsmen of a responsible society. Once people are made aware of the importance of environment in their lives, the objective of present study may be achieved for which the teachers can play a significant role. Teachers should, therefore, be given exclusive training both pre-services as well as in-services in this area so that when they go into the field, they motivate, encourage, inspire and facilitate their pupils who, in turn, will establish high values for the conservation and protection of environment.

Conclusion:

Therefore, they need to be given intensive training in environmental values. Therefore, they need to be given intensive training in environmental education so that they could acquire, sustain and develop relevant skills to impart the same to their students for making them aware of, and concerned about the environment and its associated problems, besides having the knowledge, awareness, skills, attitude, values, motivations and commitment to work individually and collectively for the restoration, conservation and improvement of environment with zeal and enthusiasm.

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